

**MONITORING OF FATIGUE INDUCED DAMAGE PROCESSES IN
CFRP BY MEANS OF THERMOMETRIC METHODS**

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ABSTRACT

The variation of dissipated energy under cyclic loading, which is detectable in form of a change of the surface temperature, was used to monitor both the development and the accumulation of damage. Typical results of different test procedures are presented. The scope of this paper is to give an overview on the possibilities of the **Thermometric Method** in case of testing carbon fibre reinforced plastic (CFRP). Results from measurements of the stiffness reduction and accompanying X-ray investigations are added.

INTRODUCTION

Thermometric methods to investigate the behaviour of metallic materials under cyclic loading are well established and lead to detailed information about microstructural processes during fatigue loading [1-3]. In the case of composites with polymeric matrices only few information exist about the change of temperature as an indicator for damage development and damage accumulation [4-10]. In the field of

nondestructive testing methods changes in the heat conduction in the vicinity of damaged regions are described [11-12]. Thermographic systems are often used to monitor a typical state of damage by heating up the composite with an external heat source (passive method) [13] or with a high frequency vibration (active method) [14]. These methods, used during a running fatigue test, normally are not able to give online information about the damage processes actually occurring or about the actual damage state. The present paper will show the possibility to use the temperature change due to fatigue loading to get information about the actual damage processes. These data will be correlated to other investigations, as the variation of stiffness. The actual damage state will be monitored by extensive X-ray examinations. The different types of heat sources, which lead to a local or integral temperature change, will be discussed.

GENERAL REMARKS ON TEMPERATURE INCREASE DUE TO CYCLIC LOADING

Polymeric materials show a heat up (warm up) due to cyclic loading as a result of internal friction and viscoelastic processes. In the case of reinforced polymers - and especially of CFRP - different kinds of influences can be stated.

- I. The heat generation can mainly be related to the matrix material used, its viscoelastic behaviour, internal friction and the amount of crosslinking.
- II. The type of fibres, the fibre volume fraction and the fibre orientation, as well as the stacking sequence of the laminate, affect the matrix loading and heat conduction and thereby the temperature increase.

In addition to these material aspects the geometrical shape of the sample or of the part influence the heat conduction just as the ambient conditions influence the heat transfer. The combination of loading conditions and test frequency determines the amount of heating. **Figure 1** shows for example the temperature increase of a sample dependent on the cyclic stress amplitude and the frequency for a sinusoidal loading.

Figure 1: Dependence of the temperature increase on the applied stress and amplitude

At $S_{max}=350 \text{ N/mm}^2$ and at a frequency of 20 Hz, this laminate, containing 0° and $^\circ/_{-45}$ layers, reaches a significantly higher temperature increase than at 10 Hz. Lower frequencies lead to a negligible temperature change. In the case of laminates, containing only 0° or 0° and 90° layers the amount of heating is smaller. This is a result of the lower interlaminar shear stresses in the matrix in comparison to the $0^\circ, ^\circ/_{-45}$ laminate. The considerable amount of temperature increase could extremely change the properties of the laminate, depending on the matrix. However, the influencing effects must be observed in the high cycle fatigue (HCF) region, where normally higher frequencies are used. The results of fatigue tests described as follows were generated in a stress and in a frequency range, where no danger of failure due to matrix heating was expected, that means failure does not occur only by matrix induced degradation processes. The temperature increase is also related to damage processes, which lead as a result of local stress transfer to a measurable change of the sample temperature.

EXPERIMENTAL SET UP AND TEST PROCEDURES

The fatigue tests were performed in a servohydraulic test machine, at a sinusoidal loading with a frequency of

10 Hz and a stress ratio of $R=S_{\min}/S_{\max}=0.1$. The temperature was measured with thermocouples (Fe-CuNi) directly stucked on the sample at different locations. To eliminate external influences on the temperature development, a special cooling circuit was mounted between the loading system and the sample, furthermore the sample was encapsulated to avoid heat convection. In addition to the temperature measurement, the variations in elongation of the test coupon during fatigue loading was monitored by using an extensometer. Using a peak-valley detector the online determination of the secant modulus was possible. In situ X-ray examination under load was also possible by mounting a X-ray tube into the load frame.

Results generated from two different test procedures will be presented. The first one works with a stepwise load increase, after a fixed number of cycles at each step. The second one is a constant amplitude load test.

EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

Figure 2 shows the result of a stepwise load increase test with a $[0_2, 90_2, 0_2, 90_2]_s$ laminate. The maximum stress was increased every 30 000 cycles. The temperature curve shows a horizontal come in, up to $S_{\max}=500 \text{ N/mm}^2$, until the end of each separate step. Further loading at higher S_{\max} -values shows a temperature increase during each load step. At $S_{\max}=750 \text{ N/mm}^2$ final failure of the test coupon is initiated. This was monitored by an extensive temperature increase.

At the end of each step, X-radiographs were taken at the maximum load. In **figure 3** the number of transvers cracks versus the actual S_{\max} -values, counted from the X-radiographs, are summarized. Up to $S_{\max}=500 \text{ N/mm}^2$ only 11 cracks could be identified. The following step led to 19 cracks. The temperature curve (fig. 2) shows a slight increase in this load range. Further loading with $S_{\max}=660 \text{ N/mm}^2$ produced 146 cracks and the temperature further increased. The sample failed during the

next step at $S_{\max}=750 \text{ N/mm}^2$. The temperature continuously increased until final failure of the sample.

Figure 2: Temperature development and stress values during cyclic loading

Figure 3: Number of cracks and stress values during cyclic loading

The temperature development in fig. 2 is a result of the matrix controlled heating, as stated above. It shows that damage induced temperature changes occur. Damage processes, e.g. crack initiation and propagation, change the stress distribution in the laminate and locally influence the load of the matrix. The temperature shows this process indirectly, but it can directly be correlated to the damage which occurs under cyclic loading. In spite of the small amount of cracks in this special laminate, the temperature

gives a proper information about the damage development. In a constant amplitude load test with the same laminate at $S_{\max}=500 \text{ N/mm}^2$, more than $4 \cdot 10^6$ load cycles were exceeded. About 40 cracks were produced with a negligible temperature change during loading. This shows that the stepwise load increase test procedure can be taken to make statements about the materials HCF behaviour, taking into account the temperature variation and especially the slope of the temperature curve.

In **figure 4** the results of two constant amplitude loading tests at $S_{\max}=670 \text{ N/mm}^2$ are plotted. The stacking sequence of the laminate was $[0_2, 90_2, 0_2, 90_2]_S$. The temperature changes and the variation in secant modulus (stiffness reduction) are shown together. The correlation between the stiffness reduction and the temperature change is clearly to be seen. The strong increase in temperature after $160 \cdot 10^3$ cycles (test coupon I) is announced by the decrease of the secant modulus. This result can be explained by a sudden initiation and a propagation of a failure in the load bearing regions of the laminate, which lead to a continuous transfer of stresses from initially damaged regions into undamaged regions due to crack initiation or crack propagation. It is followed by a continuous decrease of the secant modulus and an increase of the temperature. In the vicinity of imperfections, induced by damage, the local stress fields lead to a significantly higher loading of the matrix - if the stress transfer into the undamaged regions is not finished -, which explains the strong increase in temperature. However, after an initial increase in temperature both test coupons show a period with a constant and smooth decrease, while the secant modulus is further slightly reduced. The decrease in the temperature can be explained by a cracking process in the overstressed matrix, leading to a stress transformation into the neighbouring fibres, which effectively relieve the overall matrix loading. Therefore constant temperatures indicate an only small damage development. These results can only be achieved as long as enough undamaged regions are present, which are able to bear the load, transferred from the damaged regions without catastrophic failure. Overloading of the laminate according

Figure 4: Temperature change and stiffness reduction during cyclic loading

to the accumulated damage is indicated by an increase in temperature and a decrease of the secant modulus. Both coupons show this effect at the end of the test. In test coupon II, near the end of the fatigue life, the temperature increases before a measurable reduction of the secant modulus can be observed. Shortly before fracture the temperature decreases, while the secant modulus reaches a plateau. These effects can also be interpreted as a result of the release of the matrix stresses by a crack induced load transfer and a stable state of damage, indicated by the secant modulus. Final failure is associated with a drop of the secant modulus and a strong increase in temperature.

The results clearly show the different processes leading to a variation of the secant modulus and a temperature change. The secant modulus reacts sensitive on the transformation of stresses into the load bearing plies as a result of damage development e.g. transverse and longitudinal cracks, delamination and fibre fracture [15-18]. The temperature reacts sensitive on the damage processes influencing the matrix load. In the presence of large damaged areas, as delaminations, friction of the adjacent surfaces in the delaminated areas additionally cause higher temperatures [19].

Using more than one thermocouple gives the possibility to monitor the geometrical and the temporal development of the discontinuous damage process. In **figure 5** the results of a test are shown in which the temperature was measured at six different locations of a $[0, +/_45, 0_2, +/_45, 0]_S$ test coupon. At the measurement point 2 (T_2) a maximum temperature difference is reached after a small number of load cycles. At point 1 (T_1) an increase in temperature can also be measured. This can be a result of heat conduction or of a large damaged area reaching up to this point. This temperature has a smaller amount and is temporal shifted. During the test period a levelling of the temperature takes place. At $1.5 \cdot 10^6$ cycles at each measuring point roughly the same temperature can be observed. After $2.4 \cdot 10^6$ cycles the lines representing the temperature differences at the measuring points 5 and 6 (T_5, T_6) rise over the others. This effect results from the extension of the damaged region from point 2 to point 5 during the fatigue process.

Using thermometric methods it is easy to locate damage regions. Following the geometrical and temporal change of temperature maximums during the fatigue process, the extension of damage zones in laminates can be described.

Figure 5: Temperature change at different locations

Conclusions

The change of the surface temperature was used to investigate the fatigue behaviour of CFRP. The pronounced sensitivity of this material in heating up, dependent on the applied load and frequency, was demonstrated. Taking these results into consideration, high cycle fatigue tests should be restricted in the applied frequency, if thermal induced failure processes shall be avoided. The different damage mechanisms can also lead to a temperature change and can be detected, superposed to the general heat up. Therefore the temperature change can be used as an analogue for damage development and accumulation. Using different test procedures, statements to the long-term behaviour under cyclic loading can be made. Stress redistributions, which depend on the laminate stacking sequence, the damage state, and the load conditions as well, result in typical temperature changes. The temporal and geometrical damage development can also be detected. The fairly good correlation between the stiffness reduction and temperature change can be demonstrated. So, comparative interpretations of the fatigue processes are possible. Further investigations show the possibility to assign these results to X-ray examinations.

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